
70. The Local Bubble

OUR SUN IS THOUGHT to lie just inside the boundaries of a warm, low-density, partially-ionised interstellar cloud ($T \sim 7000$ K, $n \sim 0.1$ cm⁻³). The solar heliosphere results from the expanding high-velocity solar wind within this cloud, and extends from the Sun to about 100–150 astronomical units in the direction of its motion through space. The termination shock, marking the transition to the wider interstellar medium, was crossed by the spacecraft Voyager 1 in December 2004.

This and other nearby interstellar clouds are themselves located in a low-density region of the interstellar medium, referred to as the local cavity. This is partially filled with hot ($\sim 10^6$ K), low-density coronal gas, about 100 parsec in size, and referred to as the Local Bubble (Cox & Reynolds, 1987).

Detectable in soft X-rays, the Local Bubble was originally attributed to stellar winds from OB stars in the nearby Sco–Cen association, or to one or more nearby supernova explosions within the last 10 Myr.

THE SIZE AND SHAPE of the tenuous Local Bubble, and its precise origin, have been much debated, and many different observations have contributed to our knowledge of it today. Its dimensions can be determined directly by measuring the extent of the hot emitting bubble gas, or more indirectly by tracing the absence of absorption by neutral interstellar gas.

But the detailed morphology of the Local Bubble rests on our knowledge of the distances towards the respective line-of-sight stellar targets towards which the level of absorption is measured. Before Hipparcos, reasonably accurate distances from ground-based parallax measurements extended out to only about 20 pc.

Hipparcos distances out to 200–300 pc allowed the Local Bubble absorption characteristics to be defined with much greater certainty (e.g. Welsh et al., 1998). Sfeir et al. (1999) followed by mapping over 1000 lines-of-sight to reveal ‘interstellar tunnels’ of different widths which connect the Local Bubble to surrounding cavities. Their work supported the model of Cox & Smith (1974) in which expanding supernova-driven bubbles interact and merge to form large-scale interstellar cavities.

VARIOUS ATTEMPTS have been made to trace the origin of the supernovae that might have been responsible for the Local Bubble, with attention focusing on nearby OB associations as sites of recent star formation.

While the nearest of these, the Scorpius–Centaurus OB association, is currently about 130 pc from the Sun, Maíz-Apellániz (2001) used the Hipparcos data to extrapolate backwards in time both the Sun’s position, and those of the various association members, to show that the Sco–Cen association, and especially the Lower Centaurus Crux subgroup, was much closer to the Sun 5 million years ago, making it a likely source of the few supernovae needed to produce the Local Bubble.

Other Hipparcos-based studies also concluded that the Local Bubble could have been excavated by some 20 supernova explosions around 10–20 Myr ago, some of them perhaps as close as 40 pc (Benítez et al. 2002; Berghöfer & Breitschwerdt, 2002; Fuchs et al. 2006).

NEARBY SUPERNOVA explosions are also of great interest in understanding their consequences for the geological record on Earth, their possible effects on life, and the existential threats to life on Earth in the unlikely event of a nearby supernova explosion occurring today.

Knie et al. (2004) reported direct evidence for such an event in the form of an enhancement of the ⁶⁰Fe concentration in a deep-sea ferromanganese crust, at far above natural terrestrial levels. Produced in Type II supernovae, with a half-life of several Myr (and detectable at ratios as low as ⁶⁰Fe/Fe $\sim 10^{-16}$), iron 60 was therefore taken as a proxy for supernova debris on Earth.

Specifically, they reported an event occurring about 2.8 Myr ago, at concentrations consistent with supernova ejecta at a distance of a few tens of parsec, and thereby supporting the hypothesis of a supernova explosion within the Sco–Cen association.

This epoch, they argued, coincides with both the onset and duration of an enhanced cosmic-ray flux, and an African climate shift towards more arid conditions, attributed to the onset of a northern-hemisphere glacial event, perhaps provoking or contributing to the Pliocene–Pleistocene boundary marine extinction.

TWENTY YEARS LATER, at least before the Gaia results became available, our picture of the Local Bubble has remained largely unchanged. It is clear that the Sun lies within a cavity of low-density, high-temperature plasma surrounded by a shell of cold, neutral gas and dust. But the precise shape and extent of this shell, the cause and timescale of its formation, and its relationship to nearby star formation remained uncertain, because of inadequate knowledge of the properties of the local interstellar medium.

The picture has sharpened significantly with Gaia. From radically new spatial and dynamical constraints, derived directly from the Gaia EDR3 distances and space motions, Zucker et al. (2022) have made a revised analysis of the three-dimensional positions, shapes, and motions of dense gas and young stars within 200 pc of the Sun, enabling some striking conclusions to be made about the nature of the Local Bubble.

THEY FIRST SELECTED stars from young clusters out to 300–400 pc with a maximum age of 20 Myr, including all young clusters associated with star-forming regions currently near the surface of the Local Bubble (including the Lupus, Ophiuchus, Chamaeleon, Corona Australis, and Taurus Molecular Clouds), along with older stellar populations in the Sco–Cen association. Their sample totalled more than 1200 stars, with an average of nearly 40 stars per cluster.

They then performed a dynamical ‘traceback’ of each cluster’s motion through the Galaxy, along with that of the Sun, using a numerical model of the Milky Way’s gravitational potential (consisting of a bulge, disk, and dark matter halo), from 20 Myr ago to the present day.

Their final step was to model the expansion of the Local Bubble, using hydrodynamic simulations to study the dynamical evolution of super-bubbles driven by clustered supernovae in a uniform interstellar medium.

Based on the momentum injection required by supernovae to sweep up the total shell mass ($1.4 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$), given its present expansion velocity (around 6–7 km/s), they estimate that around 10–20 supernovae were required to form the Local Bubble. This agrees well with earlier results, from their stellar membership and an adopted Initial Mass Function, that the Upper Centaurus Lupus and Lower Centaurus Crux clusters have produced some 14–20 supernovae over their lifetimes.

THEIR RESULTING model of the Local Bubble is shown as a top-down projection of the solar neighbourhood in the first figure, and a 3D view in the second, with the Sun shown as a yellow cross at the centre. It illustrates the inner surface of neutral gas and dust, and the 3D shapes and positions of local molecular clouds delineated at a resolution of about 1 pc. Their new Gaia-era 3D model of the Local Bubble’s inner surface is shown more forcefully in their interactive model.

Their first major finding was quite remarkable: every well-known molecular cloud within about 200 pc of the Sun lies on the *surface* of the Local Bubble. These ‘surface’ clouds include not just every star-forming region in the Sco–Cen association (Ophiuchus, Lupus, Pipe, Chamaeleon, and Musca), but also Corona Australis and the Taurus Molecular Cloud, the latter lying 300 pc away from Sco–Cen on the opposite side of the bubble.

The one exception, the Perseus Molecular Cloud, at a distance of 300 pc, has likely been displaced by the recently discovered Perseus–Taurus Superbubble, also facilitated by Gaia (Bialy et al. 2021), containing Taurus on its near side and Perseus on its far side.

Zucker et al. (2022)

GOING FURTHER, they found that the young stars show an outward expansion mainly perpendicular to the bubble’s surface. Tracebacks of these young star motions support a scenario where the origin of the Local Bubble was a burst of star formation, followed by death of the most massive stars as supernovae, taking place near the bubble’s centre beginning 14 Myr ago.

The expansion of the Local Bubble created by the supernovae swept up the ambient interstellar medium into an extended shell that has now fragmented and collapsed into the most prominent nearby molecular clouds. This, in turn, provides robust observational support for the theory of supernova-driven star formation.

This animation of a flight through the Local Bubble, by Kevin Jardine, is based on data from Gaia DR2.